

EFFECT OF THE ADDITION OF BRAN MIXTURES ON DOUGH RHEOLOGY, CORRELATION BETWEEN DIFFERENT RHEOLOGICAL EQUIPMENT AND BREAD PROPERTIES

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Abstract

Cereal bran is mostly rich in dietary fiber, the use of which prevents cardiovascular diseases, diabetes, rectal cancer and obesity, on the other hand it plays an important role in the rheological characteristics of the dough and properties of bread. The aim of this research was the impact of bran mixtures on rheological properties of dough by using Brabender and Mixolab Chopin equipment, and the possible correlation between these two types of equipment and the qualitative properties of produced bread.

Therefore, in our study we used the local wheat cultivar Orovcanka to obtain flour and bran. In order to increase the level of fiber in the bread, we added mixtures of wheat bran (Orovcanka) and rye in different proportions up to 20%. In the production of bread, we also used 4% yeast, 1.8% salt, vitamin C 200 mg/kg, 0.2% SSL (sodium stearyl lactylate), and water. The dough was prepared in Mondial Forni-Italy mixer and it was baked in an oven of the same brand at a temperature of 230 °C for about 18 - 20 minutes. The determination of the physico-chemical properties was carried out in accordance with the Regulation (Official Gazette of SFRY no. 74/88). Rheological properties of the dough were performed with Brabender equipment (farinography, extensography and amylography) in accordance with ISO standards (ISO 5530-1:2013, ISO 5530-2:2012, and ISO 7973:1992). Rheological analyzes with Chopin Mixolab were performed based on the 2005 manual. While bread qualities such as bread volume, specific volume of bread and bread yield were determined based on the ICC 131:1980 method. Gained data were processed by SPSS 16 software.

Results from dough rheological analysis with Brabender equipment showed that increasing the addition of bran mixtures, one increases the water absorption which in turn delays/improves the development, stability and the degree of softness of the dough, whereas it decreases the extensibility, energy and viscosity of the dough. The maximal resistance and R/T ratio also increases. Results from the rheological analysis of the dough with Mixolab equipment showed an increase in the level of water absorption, dough consistency during mixing, protein weakening, as well as a decrease of the dough stability, starch gelatinization, amylase activity, and starch retrogradation. Correlation analysis showed a large positive signification of the results between certain parameters of the Brabender and Mixolab equipment with a significant correlation of $p < 0.01$ and $p < 0.05$. The weight and yield of bread had increased, but the specific volume and volume of bread had decreased by increasing amount of bran mixtures.

The use of bran mixtures up to 15%, as well as the use of Mixolab Chopin in rheological analyses, which had a good correlation with Brabender equipment are recommended.

Key words: *Bran mixtures, Rheological properties, Mixolab Chopin, Correlation, Bread properties.*

1. Introduction

The bread represents the most important staple food, it is consumed daily, it has a large percentage of

carbohydrates which are necessary for energy, and it has a low content of other nutrients such as vitamins, minerals and proteins [1]. Therefore, based on the high nutrient values of the bran, in the last decade one is increasingly using and creating different formulas for bread production.

Wheat bran is a by-product of milling wheat. Roller milling produces a clean separation of the bran and germ from endosperm through consecutive steps including grinding, sieving, and purifying steps [2, 3]. Schooneveld-Bergmans *et al.*, [4], reported that the wheat bran mostly consists of structural polymers such as cellulose, arabinoxilane and lignine, which provide external strength of the wheat grain and protect it against external agents. The chemical composition of the wheat bran largely depends on the wheat cultivar, the conditions of cultivation and the method of division, through the latter one determines which part of the starch is added to the aleuronic layer after the milling. In the chemical composition of wheat bran one mostly finds dietary fibers 48 - 53% and it includes: cellulose, hemicellulose, lignin and pentosane, 10 - 20% starch, at least 14.5% protein, 3% fat, 5.5 - 6.5% minerals [5, 6, and 7], and some other minor ingredients such as the group B vitamins, and bioactive compounds [8]. Kamal-Eldina *et al.*, [6], in the study they performed with the rye bran with higher content of the dimension 475mm, they concluded that they have the following chemical composition: 17.7 g/100 g protein, 4.6 g/100 g fat, 13.2 g/100 g starch, 53.1 g/100 g diet fibers, and 6.2 g/100 g ash. From health point of view, the dietary fibers are mostly used in the prevention of colon disease, prevention of stomach cancer, hypertension, and reduction of breast cancer risk, gallbladder disease and type 2 diabetes [9, 10].

Wheat bran play an important role in the rheological properties of the dough where the hydration capacity changes depending on the conditions of processing [11]. However generally the water absorption increases, and the small size wheat bran may increase the resistance of dough [12]. In addition, Banu *et al.*, [13], performed the rheology analysis with Mixolab as a result of which they came to the conclusion that with the increase of the amount of the bran, one increases considerably the dough stability, the C1 and C2 values, whereas values of C4 and C5 decrease.

However, the addition of fibers causes unwanted effect on the final bread quality. Wheat bran is more detrimental to loaf volume of bread and found to increase dough water absorption [14, 15]. Also, Katina *et al.*, [16], reported that in baking addition of wheat bran results in bread with inferior quality, low volume, poor crumb structure, poor shelf-life and a bitter flavor.

Therefore, the objectives of this study were the impact of bran mixtures on rheological properties using by traditional Brabender and the modern Mixolab Chopin equipment, the possible correlation between these two types of equipment and the qualitative properties of produced bread.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Materials

In order to study, one took the wheat cultivar Orovcanka, the most popular in our country for bread production. The flour and bran obtained for further use were stored under optimum conditions, respectively, the wheat bran was first sieved with 800 μm sieve, while the rye bran was sieved with a 1,000 μm sieve. After sieving, the bran was thermally treated (100 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, 15 minutes) and stored in the refrigerator. Different mixtures were created for rheological quality analysis and for the production of bread as in Table 1.

Table 1. The presence of wheat and rye bran in the mixtures for the rheology qualities and bread production

Mixtures	Orovcanka cultivar		Rye bran (%)
	Flour (%)	Wheat bran (%)	
M0	100	-	-
M1	95	2.5	2.5
M2	90	5	5
M3	85	10	5
M4	85	5	10
M5	80	10	10

The bread is produced based on the mixtures represented above (mixtures we used): bread yeast from "Kvasec" - Zagreb 4%, salt 1.8%, vitamin C 200 mg/kg, SSL (sodium stearoyl lactylate) 0.2%, and water, based on the absorption ability of farinograph. The preparation of dough is done in dough vessels with two spirals of type "Mondial-Forni" - Italy with two speeds. Then the dough is separated by hand in sizes of 200 g and they were given shape, were fermented in temperature 30 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ with relative humidity of 70%, and the baking was performed in electrical ovens - "Mondial Forni" - Italy at 230 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for around 18 - 20 minutes.

2.2 Methods

Determination of physico-chemical properties such as: moisture, ash content, proteins, fat, starch, cellulose and wet gluten in flour and bran was performed based on the Regulation in force [17].

Rheological properties of dough with Brabender equipment (farinograph, extensograph and amylograph) are performed in accordance with ISO standards [18, 19, and 20]. The studies with Chopin

Mixolab have been performed in accordance with the manual of 2005. The first scientists who faced this problem were Haros *et al.*, [21], and Collar *et al.*, [22]. Chopin Mixolab equipment measures in real time the torque (expressed in Nm) produced by passage of the dough between the two kneading arms, thus allowing study of rheological and enzymatic parameters: dough rheological characteristics (hydration capacity, development time, etc.), protein reduction, enzymatic activity, gelatinization and gelling of starch. The procedure followed for the analysis of the mixing and kneading behavior to the Mixolab is the following: mixing speed 80 rpm, tank temperature 30 °C, dough weight 75 g, heating rate 2 °C /min, total analysis time takes 45 minutes.

Bread quality such as bread volume, specific volume of bread and the yield of bread are all determined based on ICC method 131:1980 [23].

2.3 Statistical analysis

Results were presented as mean values \pm standard deviation (SD) of three replications. Statistical analysis was conducted using the one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) and means of results for each experiment compared, using the Duncan multiple comparison test $p < 0.05$ confidence levels. Pearson's correlation (significant level $p < 0.05$, $p < 0.01$) was used to determine the relationship between the data of Brabender (Farinograph, Extensograph, Amylograph) and Mixolab Chopin equipment. Data analysis was performed using SPSS 16.

3. Results and Discussion

In Table 2 are presented the physico-chemical properties of flour and bran which are used in the study. The moisture content is optimal for the flour and bran. The flour from cultivar Orovcanka has ash content of $0.56 \pm 0.01\%$ which is typical for flour used in bread production, while wheat and rye bran have much higher content. The protein content is slightly higher in wheat bran, while the content of wet gluten in flour is average. The fat content is higher in wheat, followed by rye bran and wheat flour. Starch is higher in flour while bran has much lower content. The highest content of cellulose has rye bran $14.72 \pm 0.70\%$, then wheat bran with $7.28 \pm 0.62\%$ and flour with only $0.79 \pm 0.08\%$, and among themselves are not significant.

3.1 Effect of bran mixtures on rheological properties with Brabender equipment's

Mixing of wheat flour with water allows the activation of viscoelastic gluten network-which determines the quality of the final product [24]. In Table 3 presented the rheological qualities of the dough obtained through Brabender equipment where one can see that with the adding of bran mixtures, the rheological qualities change significantly.

Farinograph result showed that water absorption (WA) of dough increased when bran mixtures in the flour increased from 5% to 20% (Table 3). Miš *et al.*, [25], also noticed that the fibers absorb a significant amount of water in the dough during mixing. Bran

Table 2. Physical-chemical properties of raw materials

Parameters	Moisture (%)	Ash (%)	Proteins (%)	Wet Gluten (%)	Fats (%)	Starch (%)	Cellulose (%)
Orovcanka (flour)	12.4 ± 0.26^b	0.56 ± 0.01^a	13.87 ± 0.17^a	28.1 ± 0.19	0.97 ± 0.07^a	69.18 ± 1.69^a	0.79 ± 0.08^a
Wheat bran (Orovcanka)	11.4 ± 0.17^a	4.05 ± 0.03^b	14.79 ± 0.23^b	-	4.79 ± 0.12^c	51.88 ± 1.87^b	7.28 ± 0.62^b
Rye bran	12.3 ± 0.26^b	4.32 ± 0.02^c	13.73 ± 0.25^a	-	2.77 ± 1.43^b	46.07 ± 0.95^c	14.72 ± 0.70^c

Note: Values are means \pm standard deviations (n = 3). Means with different superscript in the columns are significantly different ($p < 0.05$).

Table 3. Rheological properties of dough with bran mixtures obtained with Brabender

Mixture	Brabender								
	Farinograph				Extensograph				Amylograph
	WA (%)	DDT (min)	S (min)	DS (FU)	EX (mm)	MR (EU)	R/E	E (cm ²)	V (AU)
M0	61.8 ± 0.79^a	2.0 ± 0.5^a	0.5 ± 0.25^a	60 ± 8.66^b	156 ± 4.36^d	260 ± 5.0^a	1.7 ± 0.07^a	73.5 ± 1.04^f	900 ± 10.0^e
M1	61.9 ± 0.92^a	3.0 ± 0.75^a	2.0 ± 0.43^b	50 ± 5.0^b	148 ± 5.29^c	280 ± 8.66^b	1.90 ± 0.05^b	70.4 ± 0.88^e	850 ± 13.2^d
M2	62.6 ± 0.88^a	6.5 ± 0.86^b	2.5 ± 0.5^b	30 ± 0.0^a	124 ± 4.58^b	320 ± 10.0^c	2.60 ± 0.04^c	64.7 ± 1.15^d	750 ± 13.2^c
M3	64.5 ± 0.79^b	6.0 ± 0.5^b	3.0 ± 0.75^b	30 ± 5.0^a	95 ± 3.61^a	380 ± 13.2^d	4.0 ± 0.12^c	52.7 ± 1.22^b	690 ± 10.0^b
M4	63.2 ± 0.75^{ab}	6.0 ± 0.86^b	6.0 ± 0.86^c	20 ± 8.66^a	101 ± 3.0^a	305 ± 8.66^c	2.65 ± 0.12^c	55.1 ± 0.87^c	670 ± 10.0^b
M5	66.5 ± 0.53^c	6.5 ± 0.6^b	6.5 ± 0.66^c	30 ± 10.0^a	96 ± 3.61^a	370 ± 5.0^d	3.85 ± 0.08^d	50.7 ± 1.1^a	610 ± 17.3^a

Note: Values are means \pm standard deviations (n = 3). Means with different superscript in the columns are significantly different ($p < 0.05$)
 Brabender parameters: Farinograph: WA (water absorption), DDT (dough development time), S (dough stability), DS (degree of softening);
 Extensograph: EX (extensibility), MR (max. resistance to extension), R/E (ration resistance/ extensibility), E (energy); Amylograph: V (viscosity).

fibers are known to bind water through capillary forces or direct absorption, where during mixing and kneading is exposed to hygroscopic forces by different flour components which allow bran to pick up water molecules, and this is strongly bound to bran through formation of hydrogen bond [26]. However, bran absorbs water more slowly than flour, which delays the development of the gluten network. With which we also have longer dough development time, higher dough stability and lower degree of softening. Dough development time is significantly higher ($p < 0.05$) than the control (2 ± 0.5 min), increasing to M5 mixture (6.5 ± 0.66 min). Dough stability (S) is influenced primarily from the gluten quality and its resistance to the kneading forces [27], where also there are highly significant differences, from 0.5 ± 0.25 min for M0 to 6.5 ± 0.66 min for the M5. Degree of softening (DS) decreases or it improves from 60 ± 5 FU to 20 ± 5 FU for M4 mixture. Similar results had and Ahmed *et al.*, [28], and Rania and El kewawy [29] in their studies.

From the extensograph analyzes we notice that the extensibility (EX) is significantly lower ($p < 0.05$) than the control (156 ± 4.36 mm), decreasing to 95 ± 3.61 mm in the M3 mixture which is significant with M5 mixture. These results are similar to the results of Aziz *et al.*, [30], who in their study have used flour with different radius and they observed that with the increase of radius of the flour, there is decrease of extensibility. Maximal resistance to extension (MR) with the increase of mixture of bran increases. However the higher value is observed with M3 mixture with 380 ± 13.2 EU. A similar observation was reported in the study of Sudha *et al.*, [31], where resistance values increased with the increasing addition of wheat bran. R/E ratio increases with the addition of bran mixtures, but the control (M0) and M1 mixture have a better ratio for bread production. The area under the curve reduced from 73.5 ± 1.0 to 50.7 ± 1.17 cm² with increase of bran mixtures, and also there highly significant differences ($p < 0.05$), the values of which indicate weaker doughs. The results are similar to the results obtained by Xhabiri *et al.*, [32], who in their study have used mixture of rice

bran with dimensions of 800 μ m whereby with the increase of rice bran from 10 and 15% the energy of dough is decreased.

The viscosity values of the dough have significant differences ($p < 0.05$) and they decrease with increasing bran mixtures, but this viscosity is higher than that desired (450 - 650 AU) for bread production. These results correspond to those of study of Boita *et al.*, [33], who have used wheat bran with 25% and one observed a decrease of maximum viscosity.

3.2 Effect of bran mixtures on rheological properties with equipment Mixolab Chopin

The obtained results from Mixolab indicate that the water absorption increased with the increase bran mixtures constantly. These results are in compliance with the observation of other authors that studied different types of fibers [12, 34].

Stability of dough is significantly lower ($p < 0.05$) than the control (8.03 ± 0.13 min.) decreasing to 6.80 ± 0.11 min. in the M5 mixture.

Furthermore, the rheological properties of the dough change significantly in the process of mixing and increasing the temperature, where from Table 4 it is noticed the values of C1 and C2 increase with addition of bran mixtures, which directly depend from the time of water absorption and with it the mixing and formation of dough.

The values of C3 and C4 have significant differences ($p < 0.05$) and they decrease with increasing of bran mixtures. These results are in compliance with the results of Banu *et al.*, [13], who in their study have used wheat bran from 3 to 30%. Even the values of C5 have significant differences ($p < 0.05$), where gradually decrease by addition of bran mixtures, these results correspond to the results of Rosell *et al.*, [35], who in their study have included various fibers such are fibruline, fibrex, exafine and swelite in different ratios with flour.

Table 4. Rheological properties of dough with bran mixtures obtained with Mixolab Chopin

Mixtures	Mixolab						
	WA (%)	S (min)	C1 (Nm)	C2 (Nm)	C3 (Nm)	C4 (Nm)	C5 (Nm)
M0	58.0 ± 0.65^a	8.03 ± 0.13^c	1.08 ± 0.04^a	0.47 ± 0.02^a	2.14 ± 0.04^c	2.24 ± 0.05^c	3.51 ± 0.12^d
M1	58.7 ± 1.05^a	8.07 ± 0.16^c	1.09 ± 0.03^a	0.49 ± 0.03^a	2.09 ± 0.06^{bc}	2.18 ± 0.05^c	3.36 ± 0.09^d
M2	61.8 ± 0.95^c	7.07 ± 0.87^b	1.17 ± 0.02^c	0.51 ± 0.04^a	2.08 ± 0.04^{bc}	1.92 ± 0.07^c	2.84 ± 0.12^c
M3	59.2 ± 0.85^{ab}	8.12 ± 0.07^c	1.12 ± 0.02^{ab}	0.56 ± 0.01^b	2.07 ± 0.04^{bc}	1.80 ± 0.08^b	2.62 ± 0.12^b
M4	59.1 ± 1.01^{ab}	6.87 ± 0.09^a	1.12 ± 0.03^{ab}	0.51 ± 0.02^a	2.04 ± 0.04^{ab}	1.66 ± 0.05^a	2.39 ± 0.06^a
M5	59.9 ± 0.86^b	6.80 ± 0.11^a	1.14 ± 0.02^{bc}	0.52 ± 0.03^{ab}	1.99 ± 0.03^a	1.61 ± 0.07^a	2.47 ± 0.07^{ab}

Note: Values are means \pm standard deviations ($n = 3$). Means with different superscript in the columns are significantly different ($p < 0.05$). Mixolab parameters: WA: water absorption; S: dough stability; C1 (Nm) - maximum torque during mixing; C2 (Nm) - protein weakening; C3 (Nm) - starch gelatinization; C4 (Nm) - amylase activity; C5 (Nm) - starch retrogradation.

Table 5. Pearson's correlation between Brabender and Mixolab parameters

	WA	DDT	S	DS	EX	MR	R/E	E	V
WA	0.136	0.571	0.029	-0.388	-0.208	0.218	0.126	-0.088	-0.286
S	-0.469	-0.699	-0.556	0.701	0.440	-0.279	-0.294	0.521	0.693
C1	0.441	0.878*	0.319	-0.728	-0.611	0.583	0.519	-0.505	-0.645
C2	0.657	0.751	0.419	-0.701	-0.902*	0.920**	0.909*	-0.822*	-0.735
C3	-0.877*	-0.798	-0.559	0.776	0.821*	-0.726	-0.751	0.883*	0.948**
C4	-0.817*	-0.895*	-0.719	0.916*	0.896*	-0.768	-0.805	0.958**	0.989**
C5	-0.743	-0.922**	-0.782	0.961**	0.894*	-0.761	-0.791	0.947**	0.972**

Note: *. Correlation is significant at the $p < 0.05$; **. Correlation is significant at the $p < 0.01$.

Brabender parameters: WA (water absorption), DDT (dough development time), S (dough stability), DS (degree of softening), EX (extensibility), MR (max. resistance to extension), R/E (ration resistance/ extensibility), E (energy), V (viscosity). Mixolab parameters: WA: water absorption; S: dough stability; C1 (Nm) - maximum torque during mixing; C2 (Nm) - protein weakening; C3 (Nm) - starch gelatinization; C4 (Nm) - amylase activity; C5 (Nm) - starch retrogradation.

3.3 Correlation between of Brabender and Mixolab parameters

In Table 5 is given Pearson's correlation of Brabender and Mixolab data, from which we can observe that WA indicates a negative correlation with C3 = -0.877 and C4 = -0.817 for $p < 0.05$. DDT indicates a high positive correlation for $p < 0.05$ with C1 = 0.878 and negative correlation with C4 = -0.895, while for $p < 0.01$ it indicates a high negative correlation with C5 = -0.922. DS indicates a high positive correlation for $p < 0.01$ with C5 = 0.961 and for $p < 0.05$ it also indicates a high positive correlation with C4 = 0.916.

EX indicates a high positive correlation for $p < 0.05$ with C3 = 0.821, C4 = 0.896, and C5 = 0.894, however it also indicates a high negative correlation for $p < 0.05$ with C2 = -0.902. MR has a high positive correlation for $p < 0.01$ with C2 = 0.920. R/E indicates a high positive correlation for $p < 0.05$ with C2 = 0.909. E indicates high positive correlation for $p < 0.01$ with C4 = 0.958 and C5 = 0.947 as well as for $p < 0.05$ it has a high positive correlation with C3 = 0.883, it also indicates negative correlation for $p < 0.05$ with C2 = -0.822. V has a high positive correlation for $p < 0.01$ with C3 = 0.948, C4 = 0.989, and C5 = 0.972.

3.4 Qualitative properties of the bread produced with bran mixtures

In Figure 1 are presented the qualitative properties of the bread where we can observe that the weight of the bread does not differ significantly, even though bread M5 has a heavier weight of 177.3 g. The volume of the bread generally decreases by adding of bran mixtures, from 817.95 cm³ for the bread without bran M0 until 577.58 cm³ for bread M5, these results correspond to the results of Ahmed [36], who in their study have produced the bread from three varieties of local wheat with wheat bran.

Specific volume of the bread decreases with the increase of adding bran mixtures, from 4.95 cm³/g to 3.33 cm³/g. The obtained results are similar to the

study that was performed by XZhang *et al.*, [37], who have used the wheat bran up to 15% and they have observed the decrease of specific volume. The yield of the bread increases with the increase of adding the bran mixtures from 144.93% for bread without bran, up to 152.75% for bread with 20% of bran mixtures.

Figure 1. The qualitative properties of the bread with bran mixtures

4. Conclusions

- Addition of bran mixtures has various effects in the rheological properties of obtained dough. With Brabender equipment, at the farinograph it is observed that with the increase of the bran mixtures, there is a gradual increase in water absorption, dough development time and stability of dough, whereas the degree of softening decreases.
- At the extensograph the extensibility and the energy of dough decrease whereas the maximum resistance and the ratio R/T increase with the increase of adding the bran mixtures. The amyolytic activity decreases with the increase of adding the bran mixtures.
- From the results obtained through Mixolab Chopin, we can observe that with the increase of bran mixtures one also observes the increase of water absorption and values C1, C2, on the other hand decrease the stability of the dough, and values C3, C4, C5.
- The comparison between conventional rheological test (Farinograph, Extensograph and Amylograph) and Chopin Mixolab has indicated the existence of strong

positive correlation for certain parameters. The weight and yield of the bread increases with the increase of amount of bran mixtures, however the volume and specific volume decrease.

- Our recommendation is to use bran mixtures up to 15%, as well as use Mixolab Chopin in rheological analysis, which had a good correlation with Brabender equipment.

5. References

- [1] Young J. (2001). *Functional Bakery Products: Current Directions and Future Opportunities*. Food Industry Journal, 4, pp. 136-144.
- [2] Campbell G. (2007). *Roller Milling of Wheat*, In: Salman D. A., Ghadiri M., Hounslow J. M. (Eds.), *Handbook of Powder Technology* (Vol.12), Elsevier, Netherlands, pp. 383-419.
- [3] Peyron S., Chaurand M., Rouau X., Abecassis J. (2002). *Relationship between Bran Mechanical Properties and Milling Behaviour of Durum Wheat (Triticum durum Desf.). Influence of Tissue Thickness and Cell Wall Structure*. Journal of Cereal Science, 36, (3), pp. 377-386.
- [4] Schooneveld-Bergmans M. E. F., Beldman G., Voragen A. G. J. (1999). *Structural Features of (Glucurono) Arabinoxylans Extracted from Wheat Bran by Barium Hydroxide*. Journal of Cereal Science, 29, (1), pp. 63-75.
- [5] Apprich S., Tirpanalan Ö., Hell J., Reisinger M., Bohmdorfer S., Siebenhandl-Ehn S., Novalin S., Kneifal W. (2013). *Wheat bran-based biorefinery 2: Valorisation of products*. LWT-Food Science and Technology, 56, (2), pp. 222-231.
- [6] Kamal-Eldin A., Nygaard Lærke H., Knudsen Bach K., Lampi A., Piironen V., Adlercreutz H., Katina K., Poutanen K., Aman P. (2009). *Physical, microscopic and chemical characterization of industrial rye and wheat brans from the Nordic countries*. Food and Nutrition Research, 53, (1), pp. 1-11.
- [7] Posner E. (2009). *Wheat flour milling*. In: Khan K., Shewry P. (Eds.), *Wheat Chemistry and Technology* (4th Ed.), AACC International, St. Paul, USA, pp. 96-99.
- [8] Reisinger M., Tirpanalan Ö., Prückler M., Huber F., Kneifel W., Novalin S. (2013). *Wheat bran biorefinery - A detailed investigation on hydrothermal and enzymatic treatment*. Bioresource Technology, 144, pp. 179-185.
- [9] Hadjivassiliou M., Grunewald R. A., Sharrack B., Sanders D., Lobo A., Williamson C., Woodrooffe N., Wood N., Davies-Jones A. (2003). *Gluten ataxia in perspective: Epidemiology, genetic susceptibility and clinical characteristics*. Brain, 126, (3), pp. 685-691.
- [10] Reddy B. S., Hirose Y., Cohen L. A., Simi B., Cooma I., Rao C. V. (2000). *Preventive Potential of Wheat Bran Fractions against Experimental Colon Carcinogenesis: Implications for Human Colon Cancer Prevention*. Cancer Research, 60, (17), pp. 4792-4797.
- [11] Maskan M. (2002). *Effect of processing on hydration kinetics of three wheat products of the same variety*. Journal of Food Engineering, 52, (4), pp. 337-341.
- [12] Zhang D., Moore W. R. (1999). *Wheat bran particle size effects on bread baking performance and quality*. Journal of the Science of Food and Agriculture, 79, (6), pp. 805-809.
- [13] Banu J., Stoenescu G., Ionescu S. V. (2012). *Effect of the addition of wheat bran stream on dough rheology and bread quality*. The Annals of the University Dunarea de Jos of Galati, Fascicle VI-Food Technology, 36, (1), pp. 39-52.
- [14] Shogren M. D., Pomeranz Y., Finney K. F. (1981). *Counteracting the deleterious effects of fiber in breadmaking*. Cereal Chemistry, 58, (2), pp. 142-144.
- [15] Rogers D., Hoseney R. C. (1982). *Problems associated with producing whole wheat bread*. Cereal Foods World, 27, pp. 451-456.
- [16] Katina K., Arendt E. K., Liukkonen K. H., Autio K., Flander L., Poutanen K. (2005). *Potential of sourdough for healthier cereal products*. Trends in Food Science and Technology, 16, (1-3), pp. 104-112.
- [17] SFRY. (1988). *Regulations on product quality testing methods for the grains, bakery products, pastes and fast freezing pastes* (in Serbian). Official Gazette of SFRY No. 74/88.
- [18] ISO. (2013). *ISO 5530-1:2013: Wheat flour - Physical characteristics of doughs - Part 1: Determination of water absorption and rheological properties using a farinograph*. ISO, Geneva, Switzerland.
- [19] ISO. (2012). *ISO 5530-2:2012: Wheat flour - Physical characteristics of doughs - Part 2: Determination of rheological properties using an extensograph*. ISO, Geneva, Switzerland.
- [20] ISO. (1992). *ISO 7973:1992: Cereals and milled cereal products - Determination of the viscosity of flour - Method using an amylograph*. ISO, Geneva, Switzerland.
- [21] Haros M., Ferrer A., Rosell C.M. (2006). *Rheological behavior of whole wheat flour*. IUFoST 13th World Congress of Food Sciences Technology Proceedings, Nantes, France, pp. 1139-1148.
- [22] Collar C., Bollain C., Rosell C. M. (2007). *Rheological behavior of formulated bread dough's during mixing and heating*. Food Science and Technology International, 13, (2) pp. 99-107.
- [23] Xhabiri G., Sinani A. (2011). *Laboratory analysis of cereals, flours, doughs and baking products* (in Albanian). Chabej, Gostivar, Macedonia, pp. 111-113.
- [24] Hadnađev T. D., Torbica A., Pojić M., Hadnađev M. (2011). *The role of empirical rheology in flour quality control*. In: Akyar I. (Ed.), *Wide spectra of quality control*, Intech, Rijeka, Croatia, pp. 335-360.
- [25] Miš A., Grundas S., Džiki D., Laskowski J. (2012). *Use of farinograph measurements for predicting extensograph traits of bread dough enriched with carob fibre and oat wholemeal*. Journal of Food Engineering, 108, (1), pp. 1-12.
- [26] Onipe O. O., Beswa D., Jideani A. I. O. (2017). *Effect of size reduction on colour, hydration and rheological properties of wheat bran*. Food Science and Technology, 37, (3), pp. 389-396.
- [27] Catteral P. (1995). *Flour Milling*. In: Cauvain S. P., Young L. S. (Eds.), *Technology of bread making* (2nd Ed.), Aspen Publishers, Gaithersburg, USA, pp. 296-329.
- [28] Ahmed J., Almusallam A. S., Al-Salman F., Abdul Rahman M. H., Al-Salem E. (2013). *Rheological properties of water insoluble date fiber incorporated wheat flour dough*. LWT - Food Science and Technology, 51, (2), pp. 409-416.
- [29] Rania E. E., El kewawy H. E. (2014). *Effect of addition of stabilized rice bran on physical, rheological and chemical characteristics of pan bread*. Mansoura Journal of Food

- and Dairy Sciences, 5, (11), pp. 813-825.
- [30] Aziz M. H., Sayeddin S. M., Payghambaroost S. H. (2006). *Effect of flour extraction rate on flour composition, dough rheological characteristics and quality of flat bread*. Journal of Agricultural Science and Technology, 8, (4), pp. 323-330.
- [31] Sudha M. L., Vetrimani R., Leelavathi K. (2007). *Influence of fibre from different cereals on the rheological characteristics of wheat flour dough and on biscuit quality*. Food Chemistry, 100, (4), pp. 1365-1370.
- [32] Xhabiri G., Hoxha I., Sinani A., Sana, M. (2012). *Influence of Mixed Rice Bran in the Rheological Characteristics of Dough and Quality of Bread*. Croatian Journal of Food Technology, Biotechnology and Nutrition, 7, (3-4), pp. 167-171.
- [33] Boita E. R. F., Oro T., Bressiani J., Santetti G. S., Bertolin T. E., Gutkoski L. C. (2016). *Rheological properties of wheat flour dough and pan bread with wheat bran*. Journal of Cereal Science, 71, pp. 177-182.
- [34] Gomez M., Ronda F., Blanco C., Caballero P., Apesteguia A. (2003). *Effect of dietary fiber on dough rheology and bread quality*. European Food Research Technology, 216, (1), pp. 51-56.
- [35] Rosell C. M., Santos E., Collar C. (2010). *Physical characterization of fiber-enriched bread doughs by dual mixing and temperature constraint using the Mixolab*. European Food Research and Technology, 231, (4), pp. 535-544.
- [36] Ahmed E. G. (2005). *Effect of Bran Particle Size on Wheat flour Dough and Bread Quality*. Msci thesis, Faculty of Agriculture, University of Khartoum, Sudan, pp. 51-52.
- [37] Zhang J., Hou H., Haizhou D., Yangyong D. (2012). *Effects of bran, shorts and feed flour by ultra-fine grinding on rheological characteristics of dough and bread qualities*. African Journal of Biotechnology, 11, (15), pp. 3631-3639.